

How organizations can innovate with generative AI

Jonny Holmström ^{a,*}, Noel Carroll ^b

^a Swedish Center for Digital Innovation, Department of Informatics, Umeå University, Sweden

^b Lero, SFI Research Centre for Software, School of Business & Economics, University of Galway, Ireland

KEYWORDS

ChatGPT;
Artificial intelligence;
Innovation;
Automation;
Augmentation;
Prompt engineering

Abstract Artificial intelligence (AI) is driving significant impact on businesses across many sectors. Specifically, generative AI (GenAI) is fueling new capabilities that have triggered a wave of innovation. For example, there has been massive hype surrounding the launch of ChatGPT, with growing speculation regarding its disruptive nature for organizations and society. The ongoing debate conveys a clear belief that ChatGPT will lead to far-reaching innovation. However, it is less clear whether such innovation can be managed. We seek to close this gap by identifying distinctive innovation strategies in terms of two key dimensions: automation and augmentation (high or low). We present a new typology of four generic innovation strategies: Traditional Tool (low automation, low augmentation), Basic Automation (high automation, low augmentation), Automated Assistance (low automation, high augmentation), and Assisted Augmentation (high automation, high augmentation). These strategies differ in relation to how we view automation and augmentation for innovation, and also the risks and challenges faced throughout the process and tactics for managing the process. The typology of four generic innovation strategies pinpoints how the four strategies essentially differ not only in relation to automation and augmentation for innovation but also in terms of risks and challenges faced in the process, as well as available tactics for managing the process. Building upon this framework, our insights suggest that practitioners can harness ChatGPT effectively by aligning their innovation objectives with the appropriate strategy, whether it be enhancing creative processes or streamlining operational efficiency, thereby navigating the complexities of innovation with a more structured and strategic approach.

© 2024 Kelley School of Business, Indiana University. Published by Elsevier Inc. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

* Corresponding author

E-mail addresses: jonny.holmstrom@umu.se (J. Holmström), noel.carroll@universityofgalway.ie (N. Carroll)

1. Introduction

Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) technology (Marr, 1977; Russell & Norvig, 2016) have profoundly altered our understanding of the relationship between humans and technology across society (Huang & Rust, 2018; McCarthy & Hayes, 1987; Sundberg & Holmström, 2023). There is also a growing body of AI research, spanning several disciplines, with various attempts to model humans as cognitive machines (Konar, 2018) and initiatives to build human-like AI systems (Jain et al., 2018). AI can now assist with generating text, video, and audio content in different formats.

Generative AI (GenAI), a subset of AI, is the core technology behind tools such as ChatGPT. Released in November 2022, ChatGPT had over one million users within the first five days of its release and continues to evolve capabilities. ChatGPT improves user interaction, document analysis, and creation of visuals, thereby broadening the scope of possible applications. With APIs for DALL-E 3, GPT4 Vision, and text-to-speech—and Assistants API that makes it easier for developers to build assistive AI apps—the release of ChatGPT and its new features has altered the landscape for businesses.

For GenAI to succeed, it must consistently produce high-quality, relevant, and valuable content to meet user needs. Achieving this requires models trained on extensive, high-quality datasets and frequent updates to enhance performance. Essential resources, such as computing power and expertise, are also critical to the success of generative AI. One promising application of ChatGPT lies in conversational interfaces. Chatbots and digital assistants are potentially innovative tools for businesses to connect with customers. For example, ChatGPT can generate human-like responses to improve customer satisfaction, and may help businesses cut costs. ChatGPT also holds significant potential for innovation in content creation. As a component of a broader sociotechnical innovation network, it has the capacity to transform ideation by automating content generation processes, such as writing articles, news stories, and other forms of media. This automation holds the potential to save time and resources for content creators, allowing for faster and more accurate reporting. ChatGPT generates content ideas, which can support creative professionals such as writers and marketers. However, as tools such as ChatGPT become more widely embedded in practice, it is important to carefully

manage its impact on business and society. Even when organizations adopt generative AI, research indicates that many struggle to implement it effectively, with the majority of AI initiatives failing to gain traction or yield financial returns (Browder et al., 2022). Against this backdrop, we ask: How can organizations innovate using ChatGPT?

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. In Section 2, we explore how ChatGPT operates. In Section 3, we discuss the impact of generative AI on innovation. These insights are captured by a typology of innovation strategies, which is presented in Section 4. In Section 5, we present a discussion and conclusion, including our thoughts on the managerial implications of the typology in a rapidly evolving environment with multidimensional advances in AI and associated sociotechnical systems. Finally, in Section 6, we outline future research opportunities.

2. ChatGPT and the awakening of artificial intelligence

The search for techniques to mimic human intelligence (Mittal et al., 2017) and to exploit the relationship between computation and cognition (Pylyshyn, 1984) has heightened. There is growing interest in understanding the nature of human intelligence and reasoning to enhance augmented intelligence and decision-making (Carroll, 2021), which has been especially intense in the development of ChatGPT.

Although ChatGPT's success may be considered remarkable, its long-term effects still remain uncertain. Numerous reports have described ChatGPT as a game-changer in diverse contexts like education (Pavlik, 2023) and healthcare (O'Connor, 2022). ChatGPT is built on the GPT-3 model, as well as more recent advancements like GPT-4 and beyond, which is a large language model (LLM) with a transformer model architecture (Figure 1). A *transformer* is a deep learning model with a self-attention mechanism that differentially weights the significance of each part of input data. It is used mainly in natural language processing (NLP) and computer vision.

In this architecture, an encoder captures keywords that are important for the semantics of a sentence (or key elements of some other kind of input), and a decoder translates them to decide what parts of the sentence are important and which key terms give the sentence context (e.g., idea generation for innovation). A neural network uses two competing networks—generative

Figure 1. The transformer model architecture

Source: Wikimedia Commons

adversarial networks, or GANs—consisting of a generator and a discriminator that helps to represent human-like outputs (i.e., outputs that are seemingly indistinguishable from real data). This transfer process generates many possibilities but also potential threats for ideation to inform or influence digital innovation. By building on this architecture, ChatGPT has become a powerful tool with the potential to drive significant business transformation via digital innovation—but it is not without its issues. Among these issues, the digital innovation potential of technologies such as ChatGPT creates problems in understanding and evaluating the strategic choices available to organizations seeking to apply them in their operations. In addition, there have been growing concerns about AI hallucinations (Fui-Hoon Nah et al., 2023). A widely recognized limitation of generative AI, *AI hallucinations* refer to the content generated on a phenomenon that provides false information or facts that are not based on real data, events, or sources. This raises concerns for innovation because AI models can produce content that it has not explicitly learned since it is not directly related to its input or training data. Therefore, we need to be more systematic about how we adopt generative AI solutions like ChatGPT for innovation. Against this backdrop, we develop a typology of innovation strategies for organizations that use ChatGPT, following examples from the literature in related fields (e.g., Paswan et al., 2009; Taran et al., 2015). By developing this

typology, we aim to create useful heuristics to aid decision-makers in understanding the strengths, weaknesses, and suitability of possible strategies for adopting AI systems such as ChatGPT.

3. Generative AI and innovation

Organizations are using tool such as ChatGPT to generate new ideas for products and services. These tools are also helping to create more advanced chatbots and language models that better understand and respond to users more effectively. The key element, a *generative pre-trained transformer* (GPT), is an LLM that utilizes deep learning to generate human-like text through a model that inputs queries, generates content, and enables users to consume information. This is achieved via ChatGPT's ability to: (1) train on large volumes of varied but pertinent data and (2) learn how to develop more accurate content to address queries based on neural network architecture. Given ChatGPT's reliance on existing data, it makes it more challenging to think outside the box regarding radical innovations (i.e., to think differently, unconventionally, or from a new perspective). Yet, within a business context, ChatGPT and related solutions have significant potential to digitally transform business models and operations. With generative AI capabilities, technology systems can now arguably exhibit elements of creativity. For example, ChatGPT can be used to innovate and automate customer support conversations and quickly generate natural language responses to user queries. Chui et al. (2022) presented some examples of how generative AI like ChatGPT is being applied to innovation applications across various functions (e.g., marketing, operations, R&D). Such innovative uses of ChatGPT can help organizations remain competitive in their distinct and respective markets. For example, customer support organizations may use ChatGPT to automate conversations with customers and quickly generate highly accurate natural language responses to user queries, generate new leads, increase sales, and identify areas for product or service improvements. Organizations can use ChatGPT to create new ideas for their products and services at different levels of their business. They can also use ChatGPT to improve AI-powered chatbots by developing advanced models to better understand and respond to users more effectively.

An AI system like ChatGPT can lead to innovation in various ways. For example, it can be used to rapidly generate ideas and concepts for new products and services. ChatGPT can automate

customer support conversations and provide a quick and natural responses to their questions. Organizations are also discovering new ways to exploit ChatGPT for writing reports, detailing scenarios, creating AI prompts or reminders, and generate code for digital solutions, such as low-code or no-code innovations (Carroll et al. 2024). However, this is not necessarily new. Major technological organizations such as Microsoft, Google, and Amazon have long recognized the value of conversational commerce (Zhang et al., 2023), and the commercial interest in chatbots for customer service has increased substantially in recent years (Nordheim et al., 2019).

AI presents new opportunities for organizations to fundamentally rethink their business capabilities and understand new connections between people (e.g., staff, customers, agents of other organizations, and other relevant actors), processes, and technology through AI-enabled automation, engagement, insight, and innovation (Benbya et al., 2020, 2021). Machine learning and deep learning neural networks have high potential for automation, enhancement of innovation processes, and hence delivery of associated outcomes. Building on such technological capabilities to drive a data-driven innovation strategy, AI models and systems that offer high data analytics capacity can strongly support decision-making processes for innovation (Wu et al., 2020) and greatly reduce times to market (Fleming, 2019). Engaging affectively with technology can also significantly enhance important outcomes such as performance and innovativeness for business (Chandra et al., 2022; Kim, 2009; Trantopoulos et al., 2017). In addition, Mikalef and Gupta (2021) have shown how AI-based recommendations can help in the design and creation of new products, thereby supporting business model innovation (Lee et al., 2019). However, practitioner research suggests that although organizations are increasingly prioritizing adoption of AI, many AI projects remain somewhat experimental (Bughin et al., 2018) and they have often obtained little or no economic return on their AI investments (Benbya et al., 2020; Browder et al., 2022). Enholm et al. (2022) have also noted a lack of coherent understanding of how AI technologies create business value, and the types of business value that AI can deliver. In addition, Benbya et al. (2020, p. xx) concluded that “as AI technology is still maturing, awareness regarding the new management challenges it poses and the implications it raises for the workplace and the organization are still emerging.”

The rapidly increasing interest in deployment of AI for digital innovation and conversational AI agents suggests that their adoption will be a major driver of growth and profitability. Moreover, as chatbots acquire and embed human-like competencies, their use will become increasingly experience-oriented to improve user-related benefits and promote more immersive usage behavior (Chandra et al., 2022). Although the use of AI in business innovation has been well-documented, we need to draw more balanced insights regarding both benefits and drawbacks. According to Grewal et al. (2021), AI primarily provides benefits via customized experiences in B2C settings and via business efficiencies in B2B settings, yet Benbunan-Fich et al. (2020) noted that digital innovations can have severe negative and/or unintended consequences. For example, Nadia, a chatbot designed by the Department of Human Services (DHS) in Australia, was discontinued after public concerns over its ability to meet the needs of the disabled population (Benbunan-Fich et al., 2020).

Many business leaders recognize that AI can play a crucial role in organizations' performance but require more guidance on how their firms can deploy AI to achieve desired outcomes and promote effective digital transformation (Carroll et al., 2023; Holmström, 2022). Experiences with AI have shown that it can greatly change an organization's workforce, required skills, and ways of communicating and cooperating (e.g., Ransbotham et al., 2017). However, the interactions involved are core elements of digital transformation and are particularly relevant when initiating digital innovation efforts, which are still “understudied and poorly understood” (Kohli & Melville, 2019, p. 204).

From an incumbent's perspective, “digital innovation is closely linked to digital transformation in that it may lead to the fundamental transformation of an organization's existing structures, practices, values, roles, skills, and culture” (Oberländer et al., 2021, p. 3). The proliferation of technology and the perceived need to introduce AI-enabled smart services to maintain competitiveness (Knote et al., 2020) can result in profound changes in customer experience and value cocreation (Ostrom et al., 2015). One of the objectives when introducing AI-based chatbots is to provide 24/7 human-like service interaction at appropriate customer touchpoints and experiences (Kushwaha et al., 2021). In addition, the discovery of affordances for innovation is a key factor (Mesgari & Okoli, 2019). For example,

Vassilakopoulou et al. (2023, pp. 10–11) explained how “the discovery of action possibilities afforded by chatbots to service agents can help them to refactor communications by fusing their human competencies with chatbots’ capabilities.” However, we need to move beyond traditional chatbot use for task substitution and raise attention to human augmentation and the potential of hybrid services (Carroll, 2021; Vassilakopoulou et al., 2023) as part of a digital transformation. In addition, von Wolff et al. (2022) highlighted the lack of design knowledge for chatbots that support internal business processes as extant literature focuses on customer-facing use cases or chatbots’ economic and user-related effects that impact digital transformation efforts. For example, Zhang et al. (2023) present five organizational factors required to deploy chatbots for customer service: (1) establishment of the emerging role of the AI trainer, (2) change management, (3) competency management, (4) organizational resources, and (5) performance measures.

AI and digital transformation can also go hand-in-hand with digital innovation and chatbots. To support an organization’s adoption, Holmström (2022) presented an AI readiness framework that incorporates key dimensions of digital transformation: technologies, activities, boundaries, and goals. There are growing expectations that chatbots can support processes in digital workplaces such as customer support, information acquisition, self-service, education, training, and collaborative work (Meyer von Wolff et al., 2019). However, due to the complexities and diversity of the options, the optimal strategies to deploy them are uncertain, which may hinder decision-making and the successful identification of appropriate digital strategic avenues. In such circumstances, typologies, classifications, and taxonomies can be useful tools in science and business practice to reduce the complexity of real-world phenomena (Meyer et al., 1993; Smith, 2002). In this article, we construct a typology of digital innovation strategies to enhance understanding and strategic decision-making for organizations using ChatGPT in their operations.

3.1. Innovation through prompt engineering

Organizations are using ChatGPT to drive innovation through the use of prompt engineering. *Prompt engineering* involves creating effective instructions or questions (i.e., prompts) to generate the best responses from AI systems. Prompt engineering combines technology and strategy to ensure that the queries are well-

structured and relevant, leading to more useful outputs from models such as ChatGPT. Prompt engineering optimizes the performance of language models by developing tactical prompts, and the model is given clear and specific instructions. Through well-designed prompts, organizations can exploit AI’s potential for innovation and productivity, ensuring that it operates within safe and desirable parameters. Indeed, organizations can leverage prompt engineering for innovation in a number of ways such as business process management (Busch et al., 2023), content generation (Henrickson & Meroño-Peñuela, 2023), and entrepreneurial activity; Short & Short, 2023). We outline some examples of prompt engineering and ChatGPT (which are also applicable to other generative AI models) for innovation within a business context as follows:

- **Problem-solving:** Organizations are using prompt engineering to better understand complex issues to generate innovative solutions. Therefore, well-designed prompts can inspire GenAI to produce novel ideas, address technical problems, or explore new creative strategies.
- **Market research:** Tools such as ChatGPT are supporting organizations to automate market research and offer detailed insights into industry trends, competition, and consumer behavior. Therefore, effective prompt engineering allows organizations to gather actionable insights to enhance product development and marketing strategies.
- **Content generation:** GenAI can make content creation easier by producing high-quality marketing materials, reports, or social media posts. Therefore, creative prompts can lead to engaging and informative AI-generated content to drive business growth.
- **Decision support:** By generating prompts with tailored questions, organizations can leverage GenAI to analyze data and gain new insights to aid strategic decision-making. This can also be crucial for spotting growth opportunities, evaluating risks, and managing resources effectively.
- **Prototyping and design:** Innovative prompts can help generate new product or interface design ideas through rapid innovation cycles. Organizations can therefore use AI-created prototypes to help visualize new concepts and refine them more efficiently.

By integrating prompt engineering into key processes, organizations can fully harness tools such as ChatGPT and its potential for innovation. Using thoughtfully crafted prompts, GenAI can become a valuable resource for problem-solving, research, content creation, decision support, and design, enhancing creativity and efficiency across various business operations.

4. Innovating with ChatGPT: A typology and managerial recommendations

In this article, we argue that ChatGPT and similar generative AI models can significantly enhance innovation in various fields through automation and augmentation (Tschang & Almirall, 2021). ChatGPT can handle tasks that typically require extensive human effort. ChatGPT can generate content more quickly and at a larger scale than humans, which therefore has the potential to revolutionize industries such as journalism and advertising. Additionally, ChatGPT can automate some aspects of customer service by learning from existing customer interaction datasets. This allows organizations to introduce more automation to respond to common inquiries, freeing human employees to manage more complex or strategic issues, ultimately reducing costs for businesses and enhancing customer satisfaction.

ChatGPT supports humans with language-related tasks, for example, automatically summarizing lengthy documents, generating presentation slides from a report, or analyzing customer feedback. Such tasks may be tedious and typically time consuming. GenAI tools such as ChatGPT are saving employees time, during which they can concentrate on more strategic and creative tasks. In medical research, ChatGPT is being used to extract important information from scientific literature and allows researchers to remain up-to-date on the latest developments. This can potentially speed up the discovery of new treatments. In addition, in the legal sector, ChatGPT may be adopted to analyze documents and assist lawyers in identifying relevant precedents rapidly, thus lowering costs for law firms and enhancing client services.

Consideration of the four combinations of low and high levels of these dimensions results in a typology of four generic innovation strategies using generative AI models (Figure 2): (1) *Traditional Tool* (low automation, low augmentation); (2) *Basic Automation* (high automation, low augmentation); (3) *Automated Assistance* (low automation, high augmentation); and (4) *Assisted Augmentation* (high automation, high augmentation).

In Sections 4.1.–4.4., we describe these four types of innovation strategies for generative AI models within a ChatGPT context. We pay particular attention to the following aspects of innovation: (1) innovative solutions, (2) innovative automation, (3) automated solutions, and (4) automated efficiency. We also make improvement recommendations for each of the four types of digital innovation strategies and offer generic tactics for success. Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the four types of innovation strategies along with managerial recommendations.

4.1. Traditional tool (low automation, low augmentation)

Traditional tools for innovation in a business context typically involve low levels of automation and augmentation. These tools rely heavily on human expertise and do not leverage advanced technologies to a significant extent. As outlined in Figure 2, in this quadrant, ChatGPT provides straightforward, automated responses without significant depth or augmentation of human capability. When asked, ChatGPT can provide simple factual questions and direct, brief answers. This quadrant encompasses the use of ChatGPT that requires significant manual input and does not augment human abilities to any great extent. We explore this within the key categories of innovation using ChatGPT. For ChatGPT use, this might involve using the tool simply as a basic text editor or note-keeper; here, users do the bulk of the work and ChatGPT's AI key capabilities are not heavily leveraged. We outline examples of this in more detail in Table 2.

Within a business and innovation context, Table 2 places more emphasis on human creativity and expertise, with technology playing a supporting but not central role. These traditional tools often lack the advanced automation and augmentation capabilities found in modern AI-driven tools but remain valuable for fostering innovation and maintaining basic operational functions within a business.

4.2. Basic automation (high automation, low augmentation)

Basic automation for innovation within a business context emphasizes significant automation with minimal augmentation. In this approach, technology is largely utilized for process improvement, rather than playing an active role in the creative or innovative dimensions of business operations. Examples of this are outlined in more detail in Table 3.

Figure 2. A typology of strategies for innovating with generative AI models

In this quadrant, technology serves primarily as a tool for optimizing and accelerating existing innovation processes. It focuses on automating routine tasks and improving operational efficiency rather than actively driving creative problem-solving or idea generation. While basic automation can improve productivity, it may not significantly enhance an organization's ability to innovate beyond making processes more efficient.

4.3. Automated assistance (low automation, high augmentation)

Automated assistance is the use of technology to augment human skills and creativity within the innovation process. It combines human ingenuity with advanced tools and technologies to enhance problem-solving and idea generation. ChatGPT works as a partner rather than a standalone tool. It may not perform tasks autonomously, but it

significantly enhances human capabilities. In the context of business and ChatGPT, this could manifest itself in improved collaboration, ideation, analysis, and workflow, where the user and ChatGPT generate ideas together with the user providing some key prompts and direction. We outline examples of this in more detail in [Table 4](#).

In this quadrant, technology augments human innovation efforts by providing data-driven insights, reducing manual effort, and improving the efficiency of the innovation process. These solutions leverage the power of ChatGPT and automation to help teams achieve their innovation goals and remain competitive in the rapidly evolving business landscape.

4.4. Assisted augmentation (high automation, high augmentation)

Assisted augmentation for innovation in a business context involves a high degree of automation and

Table 1. Key managerial decisions for ChatGPT and innovation

Innovation strategy	How ChatGPT is used	Key managerial considerations
Innovative solutions	Generation of new ideas and concepts for products and services, as well as development of better AI-powered chatbots without relying heavily on automation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What data sources will feed idea generation capabilities to propose innovative solutions? • What actions are required to monitor and compare the validity of innovative solutions? • How can management trust the ability of ChatGPT to propose innovative solutions?
Innovative automation	Generation of new ideas and concepts for products and services, as well as development of better AI-powered chatbots, while relying heavily on automation to accelerate customer support conversations and quickly generate natural language responses to user queries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can ChatGPT achieve a desired business goal through innovative automation? • How can management measure ChatGPT's performance to determine whether innovative automation is proceeding as desired? • How can management regulate the action elements of innovative automation? • How can management differentiate between the decision elements (i.e., algorithms) of innovative automation and human decision-making capabilities?
Automated solutions	Automation of customer support conversations and rapid generation of responses to user queries without relying heavily on innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has an organization considered the shifting requirements or evolution of automated solutions to accomplish a process and operate within the current system? • How can an organization prepare a program of instructions and automated solutions to support digital transformations? • How can management support provision of a control system that not only generates clear, accurate instructions but also offers new capabilities for automated solutions?
Automated efficiency	Automation of customer support conversations and rapid generation of responses to user queries, while relying heavily on automation to accelerate these processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the potential ramifications of automated efficiency? • What are the potential ramifications of automated efficiency for employees, productivity, resources, strategy, innovation, and technology to improve operations and/or customer engagement?

augmentation, in which advanced technologies significantly enhance human creativity and productivity. This quadrant represents the scenario in which ChatGPT can not only answer questions automatically but also augment human thinking by providing in-depth, comprehensive, and sophisticated solutions. An example of this is when users ask complex questions and ChatGPT autonomously provides detailed explanations or solutions. It combines the power of automation and AI with human expertise to drive innovations like prompt engineering. Examples of this are outlined in more detail in [Table 5](#).

In this context, technology plays a central role in driving innovation, automating various aspects of the process, and augmenting human capabilities. The combination of high automation and high augmentation enables businesses not only to streamline their innovation processes but also create more innovative and effective solutions in a rapidly changing market environment.

5. Discussion and conclusions

GenAI tools such as ChatGPT have become a critical factor for businesses to establish and maintain

Table 2. ChatGPT and innovation with traditional tool (low automation, low augmentation)

Innovation categories	Examples of ChatGPT applications
<p>Innovative solutions</p>	<p><i>Brainstorming sessions:</i> Traditional brainstorming sessions with teams aim to generate innovative ideas, products, or strategies. In contrast, brainstorming with ChatGPT allows organizations to produce a larger volume of ideas more quickly and at scale.</p> <p><i>Design thinking:</i> This methodology focuses on creating creative, user-centered solutions for various business challenges. ChatGPT can enhance creativity and support idea generation, reinforcing the principles of design thinking and improving product development.</p>
<p>Innovative automation</p>	<p><i>Manual data analysis:</i> Using spreadsheets or basic analytical tools to examine data and identify trends or patterns. ChatGPT analyzes data to understand, process, and extract key insights from various sources.</p> <p><i>Developing prototypes:</i> Testing new business ideas or concepts with prototypes and mockups of products can be very costly and time-consuming. ChatGPT can create prototypes for customer feedback. ChatGPT 4 has recently announced multimodal capabilities that could potentially aid in the creation of visual designs for prototypes.</p>
<p>Automated solutions</p>	<p><i>Basic project management software:</i> Tools such as Microsoft Project and CoPilot help track project timelines and deliverables. ChatGPT can provide insights regarding best practices for task delegation, team management, and progress tracking toward project goals.</p> <p><i>Traditional customer relationship management (CRM) software:</i> These systems typically manage customer information and interactions without any advanced automation. ChatGPT can integrate with existing CRM systems to facilitate automated customer service, enabling chatbots to retrieve customer data and offer more personalized support.</p>
<p>Automated efficiency</p>	<p><i>Email management:</i> Basic email clients and filters can help manage and sort emails. ChatGPT enhances this process by using natural language processing and machine learning to understand and respond to emails effectively.</p> <p><i>Inventory management software:</i> This type of software can track inventory levels and orders but can lack advanced automation. ChatGPT can assist retailers by analyzing sales data, predicting demand, and providing stocking recommendations.</p>

competitiveness in today’s rapidly evolving digital landscape. However, the optimal innovation strategies vary and evolve over time. Therefore, identifying the optimal approach can be daunting. To aid such efforts, we have developed a typology of innovation strategies based on two key dimensions: automation and augmentation. The four combinations of low and high levels of these dimensions represent four generic innovation strategies: (1) Traditional Tool (low automation, low augmentation); (2) Basic Automation (high automation, low augmentation); (3) Automated Assistance (low automation, high augmentation); and (4) Assisted Augmentation (high automation, high augmentation). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to typify digital innovation strategies associated with ChatGPT and provide a conceptual abstraction of the complex associated phenomena.

We believe that our typology may contribute to the systematic deployment of such AI systems and the emerging research stream focused on them in three distinct ways. First, it provides a concerted characterization of technological renewal as an inherently contradictory information systems (IS) practice, with the need for high levels of clarity, accuracy, and stability in many contexts, in combination with rapid evolutionary innovation. Despite its practical importance, this issue has received scant attention from researchers.

Innovation strategies can vary significantly. In many cases, the best choice for a business depends on factors such as levels of automation and augmentation. By understanding the different types of innovation strategies available, businesses can make more informed decisions regarding when and how to innovate in the digital age. The four generic innovation strategies described herein

Table 3. ChatGPT and innovation with basic automation (high automation, low augmentation)

Innovation categories	Examples of ChatGPT applications
Innovative solutions	<p><i>Automated idea submission and tracking systems:</i> Using automated platforms where employees can submit ideas for consideration, but these systems do not provide AI-driven idea generation or creative suggestions. For example, ChatGPT can list related keywords for a specific role, which can also be useful for applicant tracking systems by searching for keywords related to the skills required for the job.</p> <p><i>Automated innovation contests:</i> Hosting competitions or challenges for innovative solutions, but without significant technology-driven support to generate or evaluate ideas. ChatGPT can be used to generate creative contest ideas, design interactive chatbot experiences, and automate contest management and prize fulfilment.</p>
Innovative automation	<p><i>Automated data collection and analysis:</i> Using software to gather and analyze data, such as market research or customer feedback, to support and identify innovation initiatives. ChatGPT can assist to streamline the reporting process by summarizing key findings, visualizing data, and providing key explanations. Therefore, by integrating ChatGPT into their workflow, analysts can generate detailed reports with minimal effort.</p> <p><i>Automated trend monitoring:</i> Adopting tools that automatically monitor industry trends and businesses informed of emerging opportunities. ChatGPT can produce human-like descriptions that are easy for people to consume, making it a powerful asset for more predictive analytics. ChatGPT can support to analyze large data sets, identify patterns, and generate accurate predictions.</p>
Automated solutions	<p><i>Basic AI chatbots for customer inquiries:</i> AI chatbots can respond to common customer questions and automate routine customer services. For example, ChatGPT can enhance customer service by assisting with queries, providing information, or troubleshooting issues and offering general support to users.</p> <p><i>Automated reporting tools:</i> Generating standard reports based on predefined templates can reduce the need for manual report creation. ChatGPT can leverage its deep learning capabilities to better understand data and identify patterns and trends, enabling it to also analyze new financial data and generate insightful reports.</p>
Automated efficiency	<p><i>Workflow automation:</i> Organizations can introduce automation to streamline the innovation process by automating task assignments, notifications, and project management. For example, ChatGPT can enhance business processes or workflows by training their models on specific tasks or information related to the business, such as frequently asked questions or common customer interactions.</p> <p><i>Resource allocation automation:</i> Using software to efficiently allocate resources and budget resources for innovation projects. For example, ChatGPT can automate how tasks are assigned and ensure that tasks are assigned to appropriate team members and deadlines are met.</p>

provide a valuable framework for businesses to leverage automation and innovation to reach their goals. Building on this, we argue that ChatGPT is a game-changer in three key ways.

First, ChatGPT fosters a level of innovation that has surpassed our usual expectations and impacts on innovation. One way that ChatGPT can drive higher levels of innovation is by lowering costs and boosting efficiency across different industries. For example, in customer service, we outline how ChatGPT can automate interactions

with customers, reducing the reliance on human representatives and cutting down service costs. Additionally, ChatGPT can unlock new capabilities that were previously unattainable. For example, ChatGPT or other GenAI tools can create more personalized educational content tailored to students' performance. It can also produce novel forms of creative content—including writing, poetry, and music—which opens up new opportunities for artists, writers, and the entertainment industry at large.

Table 4. ChatGPT and innovation with automated assistance (low automation, high augmentation)

Innovation categories	Examples of ChatGPT applications
Innovative solutions	<p><i>Collaborative innovation platforms:</i> These platforms facilitate idea generation and collaboration among employees, often using AI-driven recommendation systems to suggest innovative concepts and solutions. ChatGPT can better organize the community workspace, improving accessibility, knowledge sharing, and team collaboration.</p> <p><i>Ideation software:</i> Tools that use AI to support brainstorming sessions, providing prompts, and helping participants expand their creative thinking. Incorporating ChatGPT into this process can enhance creativity and lead to new perspectives and diverse solutions.</p>
Innovative automation	<p><i>Machine learning algorithms for idea ranking:</i> Utilizing algorithms to rank and prioritize innovative ideas generated by teams, helping identify the most promising concepts. ChatGPT provides a useful sounding board and has significant potential to use this tool as a brainstorming partner. Users can feed ChatGPT with some details about the business, brand, product, or service and seek assistance in generating content ideas.</p> <p><i>ChatGPT-powered market trend analysis:</i> Organizations can use AI capabilities to automatically analyze market trends and competitive landscape to enable businesses to identify opportunities for innovation. ChatGPT has the ability to identify emerging trends by exploring patterns that can provide businesses with the opportunity to be early adopters.</p>
Automated solutions	<p><i>Automated customer feedback analysis:</i> AI-powered sentiment analysis tools can automatically extract key insights from customer feedback and provide actionable suggestions for product or service improvements.</p> <p><i>AI-driven patent search:</i> ChatGPT can help organizations identify potential areas for innovation by searching and categorizing patents using natural language processing and machine learning.</p>
Automated efficiency	<p><i>Workflow automation:</i> Organizations can implement automation tools that streamline innovation processes by handling routine tasks such as data entry, scheduling, and notifications. ChatGPT can automate business processes or workflows by training models that can be used to generate test cases and test data for automated testing systems.</p> <p><i>Automated idea tracking:</i> Using software to manage and track the progress of innovation projects, organizations can move from idea submission to implementation. ChatGPT can be prompted to generate more diverse thinking to build campaigns for new business ideas.</p>

In this context, the proposed typology provides a framework for understanding and measuring the digital innovation linked to ChatGPT and its future potential.

Second, it can drive disruptive innovation in certain areas, including higher education and beyond. One possible application is the development of automated tutors or teaching assistants. ChatGPT could be trained on educational materials to respond to students' inquiries and offer explanations that replicate human interaction. This has the potential to make education more accessible and cost-effective by decreasing the reliance on human teachers in specific scenarios. Furthermore, within an e-learning context, ChatGPT is being used as a digital assistant to create personalized learning experiences by delivering customized content and

feedback tailored to students' performance. In other industries, ChatGPT could automate customer service interactions, enhance operational efficiency, and generate creative content in fields such as writing and advertising.

Third, it leads to a need for better understanding of the dynamics of the algorithms involved, which are by no means transparent. Clearly, the inner workings of models like those incorporated in ChatGPT are not fully understood and can be difficult for nonexperts to interpret. The model takes input data and produces output data, but the processes involved are not easy to interpret. This can inhibit understanding of how the model makes its predictions, as well as the identification of potential biases or errors in its output.

Table 5. ChatGPT and innovation with assisted augmentation (high automation, high augmentation)

Innovation categories	Examples of ChatGPT applications
Innovative solutions	<p><i>AI-powered product design:</i> Using AI to generate design ideas and prototypes for new products or product enhancements, accelerating the innovation process. ChatGPT can create personas, simulate interviews with fictional users, generate design ideas, select the best ideas, envision them as detailed product features, simulate fictional usage scenarios and conversations between a prototype app and fictional users, and evaluate users.</p> <p><i>Predictive analytics for market trends:</i> Leveraging machine learning to predict emerging market trends. This supports organizations to be more proactive about developing innovative solutions that meet emerging market demands. For example, ChatGPT utilizes deep learning algorithms to analyze and interpret vast amounts data, making it an excellent tool for predicting market trends.</p>
Innovative automation	<p><i>Automated idea generation:</i> AI algorithms can autonomously generate innovative ideas based on predefined criteria. In practical terms, this can help teams to kickstart their creative process. In addition, by analyzing the transcript of a team's brainstorming session, ChatGPT can identify related ideas and examples that the team might not have considered, offering fresh inspiration and direction.</p> <p><i>Automated concept testing:</i> Organizations can exploit AI-driven tools for concept testing that analyzes customer feedback and assesses the viability of new concepts. Through the use of prompt engineering, ChatGPT can generate a detailed test plan, which might include specific setup instructions and multiple test cases.</p>
Automated solutions	<p><i>Chatbots for customer support:</i> Organizations can implement AI chatbots to manage customer inquiries, complaints, and general issues. This can enhance customer service with automated solutions. For example, ChatGPT can personalize the overall customer service experience and do so at scale.</p> <p><i>AI-driven content creation:</i> Organizations are exploiting ChatGPT capabilities to generate written content (e.g., reports, articles, marketing materials). This can reduce the need for manual content creation. In addition, ChatGPT can also help to deliver more engaging, thoughtful, and conversational responses for various applications.</p>
Automated efficiency	<p><i>Workflow orchestration:</i> AI-driven workflow automation systems can support to better manage end-to-end innovation processes. This can span from idea generation to product development, optimizing efficiency. By analyzing data from across multiple sources, ChatGPT can offer more informed recommendations to streamline workflows.</p> <p><i>Automated project management:</i> Organizations can implement AI-based project management tools to help with allocating resources, monitoring progress, and optimizing schedules across projects. ChatGPT can assist project managers with many aspects of this by automating certain tasks and managing resources more effectively. This can range from creating project plans, to tracking progress, to identifying risks, to generating documentation, to answering specific queries.</p>

Considering the ways in which ChatGPT is likely to be a game-changer for organizations, it is crucial for managers to improve their understanding of how to innovate with ChatGPT. Against this backdrop, our study and developed typology provide new insights and several important implications for managers engaged with digital innovation associated with ChatGPT at strategic and operational levels. Heuristics based on the typology may help managers develop effective

innovation strategies involving ChatGPT's adoption and deployment more systematically. The four generic innovation types differ in required management considerations, staff competence, associated risks, and challenges. Differentiation across these aspects should allow managers to circumvent an ad hoc manner of decision-making and apply a more systematic, careful approach in the identification, estimation of costs and benefits, and overall assessment of available digital

innovation options. This, in turn, should lead to better resource management, increased development of new capabilities, higher returns on upfront investment in digital innovation efforts, and the adoption of generative AI models like ChatGPT.

6. Future research opportunities

Organizations have multiple ways to innovate with ChatGPT. First, they can leverage ChatGPT for rapid problem-solving and idea generation, fostering creative solutions to complex challenges. ChatGPT can also enhance research skills and content creation, enabling data-driven decisions and high-quality outputs. ChatGPT can also automate customer support, improving the user experience while also saving valuable human time and resources. Further, GenAI tools such as ChatGPT can drive disruptive innovation across certain sectors; consider, for example, digital assistants or automated teaching assistants. ChatGPT is being trained on educational materials and research resources to respond to students' inquiries and offer explanations that replicate human interaction. This also has the potential to make education more accessible and cost-effective in specific scenarios. We outline how ChatGPT within an e-learning context could also create personalized learning experiences in businesses by delivering customized content and feedback. In other industries,

ChatGPT is being adopted to automate customer service interactions, enhance operational efficiency, and generate creative content in fields such as writing and advertising. This technology also supports prototyping and design by generating fast, innovative concepts. In summary, ChatGPT provides organizations with a versatile tool to increase efficiency, spark innovation, and meet diverse business needs. This also prompts numerous opportunities for future research in those areas and new frontiers for business and information systems research. Future research on how organizations innovate with ChatGPT can be categorized into the four innovation strategies (Table 6).

ChatGPT brings sociotechnical systems to the forefront for practitioners and researchers alike. One key principle related to sociotechnical systems is that they are designed to enhance human and technological capabilities. Therefore, tools such as ChatGPT can offer some flexibility and adaptability to cater to the preferences and needs of individual users. From a sociotechnical standpoint, this is demonstrated by ChatGPT's capacity to handle diverse topics and tasks, and its ability to learn and adjust to the specific innovation requirements and preferences of each user. ChatGPT embodies the notion of collaboration and participation, uniting diverse groups of people toward common innovation goals. Coupled with the outlined research directions, this sociotechnical

Table 6. Summary of future research opportunities on how organizations can innovate with ChatGPT

ChatGPT innovation category	Future research opportunities
Traditional tool (low automation, low augmentation)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluate the impact of carefully crafted human-centered prompts in fostering creative thinking and problem-solving in organizations. 2. Explore how expertly designed prompts can facilitate more effective brainstorming and idea generation in line with traditional innovation practices.
Basic automation (high automation, low augmentation)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Investigate how AI-driven prompt generation can streamline processes and how prompts improve efficiency and effectiveness. 4. Examine the key benefits and drawbacks of automated prompts in streamlining routine innovation tasks (e.g., market research, data analytics) and freeing up human resources for more creative endeavors.
Automated assistance (low automation, high augmentation)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Examine how AI-powered prompts can act as creative collaborators, enhancing idea generation and innovation strategy development. 6. Analyze how AI can boost human creativity through innovative prompts, potentially leading to breakthrough ideas and solutions.
Assisted augmentation (high automation, high augmentation)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Explore how AI-generated prompts and AI assistance have altered the innovation processes. 8. Examine how integrated AI systems support or hinder innovation, across key tasks such as idea generation and problem-solving to prototype creation and decision-making.

system perspective will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of how prompt engineering with ChatGPT can align with different innovation strategies within organizations. By categorizing future research into this typology, organizations can tailor their approach to ChatGPT integration based on their specific innovation needs and goals.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Science Foundation Ireland Grant 13/RC/2094_2. Support was also provided by the University of Galway Strategic Fund (Citizen Development Lab).

References

- Benbunan-Fich, R., Desouza, K. C., & Andersen, K. N. (2020). IT-enabled innovation in the public sector: Introduction to the special issue. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 29(4), 323–328.
- Benbya, H., Davenport, T. H., & Pachidi, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence in organizations: Current state and future opportunities. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 19(4), ix–xxi.
- Benbya, H., Pachidi, S., & Jarvenpaa, S. (2021). Artificial intelligence in organizations: Implications for information systems research. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 22(2), 281–303.
- Browder, R. E., Koch, H., Long, A., & Hernandez, J. M. (2022). Learning to innovate with big data analytics in interorganizational relationships. *Academy of Management Discoveries*, 8(1), 139–166.
- Bughin, J., Seong, J., Manyika, J., Chui, M., & Joshi, R. (2018). Notes from the AI frontier: Modeling the impact of AI on the world economy. *McKinsey*. Available at <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/artificial-intelligence/notes-from-the-ai-frontier-modeling-the-impact-of-ai-on-the-world-economy>
- Busch, K., Rochlitz, A., Sola, D., & Leopold, H. (2023). Just tell me: Prompt engineering in business process management. In *International Conference on Business Process Modeling, Development, and Support* (pp. 3–11). Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature.
- Carroll, N. (2021). Augmented intelligence: An actor-network theory perspective. In *Proceedings of the 29th European Conference on Information Systems*. Available at https://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2021_rp/
- Carroll, N., Hassan, N. R., Junglas, I., Hess, T., & Morgan, L. (2023). Transform or be transformed: The importance of research on managing and sustaining digital transformations. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 32(3), 347–353.
- Carroll, N., Holmström, J., & Matook, S. (2024). Transforming business with low-code and no-code. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 23(3), pp. xvii–xxv.
- Chandra, S., Shirish, A., & Srivastava, S. C. (2022). To be or not to be... human? Theorizing the role of human-like competencies in conversational artificial intelligence agents. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 39(4), 969–1005.
- Chui, M., Roberts, R., & Yee, L. (2022). Generative AI is here: How tools like ChatGPT could change your business. *McKinsey*. Available at <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/quantumblack/our-insights/generative-ai-is-here-how-tools-like-chatgpt-could-change-your-business>
- Enholm, I. M., Papagiannidis, E., Mikalef, P., & Krogstie, J. (2022). Artificial intelligence and business value: A literature review. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 24(5), 1709–1734.
- Fleming, P. (2019). Robots and organization studies: Why robots might not want to steal your job. *Organization Studies*, 40(1), 23–38.
- Fui-Hoon Nah, F., Zheng, R., Cai, J., Siau, K., & Chen, L. (2023). Generative AI and ChatGPT: Applications, challenges, and AI-human collaboration. *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research*, 25(3), 277–304.
- Grewal, D., Guha, A., Satornino, C. B., & Schweiger, E. B. (2021). Artificial intelligence: The light and the darkness. *Journal of Business Research*, 136, 229–236.
- Henrickson, L., & Meroño-Peñuela, A. (2023). Prompting meaning: A hermeneutic approach to optimising prompt engineering with ChatGPT. *AI & Society*. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01752-8>
- Holmström, J. (2022). From AI to digital transformation: The AI readiness framework. *Business Horizons*, 65(3), 329–339.
- Huang, M. H., & Rust, R. T. (2018). Artificial intelligence in service. *Journal of Service Research*, 21(2), 155–172.
- Jain, H., Padmanabhan, B., Pavlou, P. A., & Santanam, R. T. (2018). Call for papers - Special issue of Information Systems Research: Humans, algorithms, and augmented intelligence: The future of work, organizations, and society. *Information Systems Research*, 29(1).
- Kim, S. S. (2009). The integrative framework of technology use: An extension and test. *MIS Quarterly*, 33(3), 513–537.
- Knote, R., Janson, A., Söllner, M., & Leimeister, J. M. (2020). Value co-creation in smart services: A functional affordances perspective on smart personal assistants. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 22(2), 418–458.
- Kohli, R., & Melville, N. P. (2019). Digital innovation: A review and synthesis. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(1), 200–223.
- Konar, A. (2018). *Artificial intelligence and soft computing: Behavioral and cognitive modeling of the human brain*. Boca, Raton, FL: CRC Press.
- Kushwaha, A. K., Kumar, P., & Kar, A. K. (2021). What impacts customer experience for B2B enterprises on using AI-enabled chatbots? Insights from big data analytics. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 98, 207–221.
- Lee, J., Suh, T., Roy, D., & Baucus, M. (2019). Emerging technology and business model innovation: The case of artificial intelligence. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 5(3), 44.
- Marr, D. (1977). Artificial intelligence — A personal view. *Artificial Intelligence*, 9(1), 37–48.
- McCarthy, J., & Hayes, P. J. (1987). *Some philosophical problems from the standpoint of artificial intelligence*. Burlington, VT: Morgan Kaufmann.
- Mesgari, M., & Okoli, C. (2019). Critical review of organisation-technology sensemaking: Towards technology materiality, discovery, and action. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 28(2), 205–232.
- Meyer, A. D., Tsui, A. S., & Hinings, C. R. (1993). Configurational approaches to organizational analysis. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(6), 1175–1195.
- Meyer von Wolff, R., Hobert, S., & Schumann, M. (2019). How may I help you? State of the art and open research questions for chatbots at the digital workplace. In *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. Wailea, HI: HICSS.

- Mikalef, P., & Gupta, M. (2021). Artificial intelligence capability: Conceptualization, measurement calibration, and empirical study on its impact on organizational creativity and firm performance. *Information and Management*, 58(3), Article 103434.
- Mittal, N., Lowes, P., Ronanki, R., Wen, J., & Sharma, S. (2017). *Machine intelligence: Technology mimics human cognition to create value*. New York, NY: Deloitte University Press.
- Nordheim, C. B., Følstad, A., & Bjørkli, C. A. (2019). An initial model of trust in chatbots for customer service—findings from a questionnaire study. *Interacting with Computers*, 31(3), 317–335.
- O'Connor, S. (2022). Open artificial intelligence platforms in nursing education: Tools for academic progress or abuse? *Nurse Education in Practice*, 66, Article 103537.
- Oberländer, A. M., Röglinger, M., & Rosemann, M. (2021). Digital opportunities for incumbents—A resource-centric perspective. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 30(3), Article 101670.
- Ostrom, A. L., Parasuraman, A., Bowen, D. E., Patrício, L., & Voss, C. A. (2015). Service research priorities in a rapidly changing context. *Journal of Service Research*, 18(2), 127–159.
- Paswan, A., D'Souza, D., & Zolfagharian, M. A. (2009). Toward a contextually anchored service innovation typology. *Decision Sciences*, 40(3), 513–540.
- Pavlik, J. V. (2023). Collaborating with ChatGPT: Considering the implications of generative artificial intelligence for journalism and media education. *Journalism and Mass Communication Educator*, 78(1), 84–93.
- Pylyshyn, Z. W. (1984). *Computation and cognition*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Ransbotham, S., Kiron, D., Gerbert, P., & Reeves, M. (2017). *Reshaping business with artificial intelligence: Closing the gap between ambition and action*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Russell, S., & Norvig, P. (2016). *Artificial intelligence: A modern approach*. London, UK: Pearson.
- Short, C. E., & Short, J. C. (2023). The artificially intelligent entrepreneur: ChatGPT, prompt engineering, and entrepreneurial rhetoric creation. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 19, Article e00388.
- Smith, K. B. (2002). Typologies, taxonomies, and the benefits of policy classification. *Policy Studies Journal*, 30(3), 379–395.
- Sundberg, L., & Holmström, J. (2023). Democratizing artificial intelligence: How no-code AI can leverage machine learning operations. *Business Horizons*, 66(6), 777–788.
- Taran, Y., Boer, H., & Lindgren, P. (2015). A business model innovation typology. *Decision Sciences*, 46(2), 301–331.
- Trantopoulos, K., von Krogh, G., Wallin, M. W., & Woerter, M. (2017). External knowledge and information technology: Implications for process innovation performance. *MIS Quarterly*, 41(1), 287–300.
- Tschang, F. T., & Almirall, E. (2021). Artificial intelligence as augmenting automation: Implications for employment. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 35(4), 642–659.
- Vassilakopoulou, P., Haug, A., Salvesen, L. M., & Pappas, I. O. (2023). Developing human/AI interactions for chat-based customer services: Lessons learned from the Norwegian government. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 32(1), 10–22.
- von Wolff, R. M., Hobert, S., & Schumann, M. (2022). Designing process-based chatbots in enterprises: The case of business travel organization considering the users' perspective and business value. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*, 14(4), 578–623.
- Wu, L., Hitt, L., & Lou, B. (2020). Data analytics, innovation, and firm productivity. *Management Science*, 66(5), 2017–2039.
- Zhang, J. J., Følstad, A., & Bjørkli, C. A. (2023). Organizational factors affecting successful implementation of chatbots for customer service. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 22(1), 122–156.